

Rare Anomaly with Accessory Hepatic Lobe in Symptomatic Gall Bladder Surgery in Saudi Population: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT Aim: to aware the presence of hepatic anomaly with accessory hepatic lobe (AHL) of the liver during surgery of symptomatic gallstones. The accessory hepatic lobe of the liver (AHL) either in continuity with the proper liver parenchyma or embedded in the tissue not connected with the liver as ectopic hepatic lobe (EHL) has been labelled in a rare category. **Case report:** In Saudi Arab two consequent cases in patients aged by 21 and 38 years presented with cholecystitis and cholelithiasis reported in the same hospital in 6 months duration. One was seen during laparoscopic cholecystectomy, and another confirmed on histopathological examination. **Conclusion:** Above study showed quiescent AHL, therefore, left untreated. EHL which was found on the surface of gall bladder was excised along with stone containing gall bladder during cholecystectomy. AHL although rare but not infrequent and is usually diagnosed intraoperatively. Its possible existence either in continuity with the liver or as an ectopic hepatic tissue during any kind of surgery (abdominal, thoracic) must be in knowledge because if it goes into serious complications, will change the whole treatment strategy and needs its concomitant resection.

KEYWORDS Accessory hepatic lobe, ectopic liver tissue, cholelithiasis, cholecystitis, laparoscopic surgery

Introduction

Accessory hepatic liver first described by Morgagni in 1767.[1] Its incidence is estimated to be less than 1% based upon the series of 1802 patients during laparoscopy in the study done in Japan.[2] Accessory liver lobe most commonly occurs under the surface of the liver, gastrohepatic ligament, gall bladder, near the umbilicus, adrenal glands and pancreas. [3] AHL appears either as a sessile, wide base mass continuous with liver parenchyma proper (Reidel's lobe) or pedunculated one carrying its blood supply susceptible to torsion due to its absence of ligamentous attachment.[4] Ectopic liver lobe is also called as the accessory

lobe but not in continuity with mother liver. Small EHL does not have complete functional architecture and is metabolically handicapped, facilitating the carcinogenetic process. In one study 9 out of 70 cases of EHL developed hepato carcinogenesis 6 out of 22 cases (27%) was cirrhotic; therefore it is wise to remove EHL to prevent complications.[5] Herein we report two cases with the accessory hepatic lobe. One was in continuity with the native liver parenchyma and another with ectopic liver tissue found over the dorsal surface of the stone containing gall bladder.

Case 1

A 21-year-old boy presented with a history of recurrent pain in the right upper quadrant for four days. It was gradual in onset, continuous, mild to moderate in intensity, colicky in nature, radiating to mid back region and aggravated after eating a fatty meal and relieved by taking medicines. According to him, he observed a similar type of pain six months ago which was gradual in onset moderate to severe in intensity and colicky in nature and relieved by taking medicines. On abdominal examination elicited Murphy's sign was positive. His haema-

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Figure 1: Accessory lobe in the inferomedial surface of the left lobe of liver covering the ventral surface of the gastric pyloric canal.

tology and biochemical reports appeared within normal limits. Ultrasound showed multiple gall stones, thick wall gall bladder and pericholecystic fluid. After taking general measures and anaesthesia fitness, laparoscopic cholecystectomy planned. A preoperative finding revealed stone containing gall bladder and sessile wide base accessory hepatic lobe in the infero medial surface of the native liver and was around 3x5 cm sized. It is depicted in figure I & II. As the accessory liver lobe found with normal liver parenchymal architecture; therefore it was left untreated at the same time routine cholecystectomy was performed. Postoperative period remained uneventful.

Case 2

A 38-year-old female presented in ER with right upper quadrant epigastric region pain for 6 hours radiating to the mid back region. It was colicky in nature, continuous and moderate to severe in intensity. It was associated with nausea and three episodes of vomiting containing food particles. No significant history was elicited. Her radiology revealed stones in the gall bladder and phlegmonous collection around gallbladder. She was put on intravenous fluids, antibiotics and analgesics after general measures and resuscitation within 72 hours of an acute attack of cholecystitis laparoscopic cholecystectomy planned. Per-operative findings revealed some flimsy omental adhesions around gall bladder which were removed by blunt dissection. At the dorsal surface of gall bladder fundus a small, sessile, broad-based 5x3 cm sized tissue similar to liver parenchyma seen. See figure III & IV. It was left undisturbed, and the gall bladder was removed as a part of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Postoperatively histopathology of the specimen confirmed the presence of accessory hepatic parenchyma and got the name of ectopic hepatic liver tissue (EHL).

Discussion

AHL may remain asymptomatic or manifested as inflammation or torsion of either gall bladder or accessory liver itself resulting in ischemia of gall bladder or whole native liver. [6, 7, 8] In our case, both rarities remained quiescent. The study done

Figure 2: Laparoscopic view of the accessory liver.

Figure 3: Laparoscopic view of ectopic liver tissue on the dorsal surface of the gall bladder.

Figure 4: Biopsy specimen. Ectopic liver lobe on the dorsal surface of the gallbladder.

in 2011 showed the presence of AHL with abdominal wall defect of various types. E.g. cloacal exstrophy, umbilical hernia, congenital diaphragmatic hernia or omphalocele. The theory behind this association may be due to heteroplastic development of accessory liver which impedes the closure of the umbilical ring.[4] Comparative to above study our cases were associated with acute and acute on chronic cholecystitis with cholelithiasis in young patients. Riedel's described a tongue like protrusion in the inferior surface of right lobe of liver known as Riedel's lobe and is the most common anatomical variant of the accessory hepatic lobe, corresponding to hypertrophy of segments V and VI.[9] While AHL can simulate tumours, there have also been reports of hepatocellular carcinoma that developed in these accessory lobes.[10] Based on a review of the literature, our case update focuses on the accessory hepatic lobe.

Ectopic hepatic lobe (EHL) is usually an incidental finding during laparoscopy, laparotomy or autopsy performed for unrelated reasons, most commonly for diseases of the gallbladder.[11]

EHL can be found in the thoracic cavity and causing diagnostic dilemma and is differentiated by benign lesion only by histopathology.[12] Similarly our case report with EHL on the dorsal surface of gall bladder & was confirmed after surgery on biopsy.

Management of AHL is based on its manifestation. Resection of AHL is only proposed in serious complications either; acute in the form of torsion or chronic as persistent hepatic dysfunction e.g. hepatocellular carcinoma or focal nodular hyperplasia.[13] In our study AHL remain silent during the inflammation of gall bladder, and it was left untreated.

Conclusion

Above study showed quiescent AHL, therefore, left untreated. EHL which was found on the surface of gall bladder was excised along with stone containing gall bladder during cholecystectomy.

AHL although rare but not infrequent and is usually diagnosed intraoperatively. Its possible existence either in continuity with the liver or as an ectopic hepatic tissue during any kind of surgery (abdominal, thoracic) must be in knowledge because if it goes into serious complications, will change the whole treatment strategy and needs its concomitant resection.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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